

Smarandache fantastic ideals of Smarandache BCI-algebras

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Abstract The notion of Smarandache fantastic ideals is introduced, examples are given, and related properties are investigated. Relations among Q -Smarandache fresh ideals, Q -Smarandache clean ideals and Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals are given. A characterization of a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal is provided. The extension property for Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals is established.

Keywords Smarandache BCI-algebra, Smarandache fresh ideal, Smarandache clean ideal, Smarandache fantastic ideal

1. Introduction

Generally, in any human field, a Smarandache structure on a set A means a weak structure W on A such that there exists a proper subset B of A which is embedded with a strong structure S . In [5], W.B.Vasantha Kandasamy studied the concept of Smarandache groupoids, sub-groupoids, ideal of groupoids, semi-normal subgroupoids, Smarandache Bol groupoids and strong Bol groupoids and obtained many interesting results about them. Smarandache semi-groups are very important for the study of congruences, and it was studied by R.Padilla [4]. It will be very interesting to study the Smarandache structure in BCK/BCI-algebras. In [1], Y.B.Jun discussed the Smarandache structure in BCI-algebras. He introduced the notion of Smarandache (positive implicative, commutative, implicative) BCI-algebras, Smarandache sub-algebras and Smarandache ideals, and investigated some related properties. Also, he studied Smarandache ideal structures in Smarandache BCI-algebras. He introduced the notion of Smarandache fresh ideals and Smarandache clean ideals in Smarandache BCI-algebras, and investigated its useful properties. He gave relations between Q -Smarandache fresh ideals and Q -Smarandache clean ideals, and established extension properties for Q -Smarandache fresh ideals and Q -Smarandache clean ideals (see [2]). In this paper, we introduce the notion of Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals, and investigate its properties. We give relations among Q -Smarandache fresh ideals, Q -Smarandache clean ideals and Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals. We also provide a characterization of a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal. We finally establish the extension property for Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals.

2. Preliminaries

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a BCI-algebra if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (a1) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) (((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0)$,
- (a2) $(\forall x, y \in X) ((x * (x * y)) * y = 0)$,
- (a3) $(\forall x \in X) (x * x = 0)$,
- (a4) $(\forall x, y \in X) (x * y = 0, y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y)$.

If a BCI-algebra X satisfies the following identity:

- (a5) $(\forall x \in X) (0 * x = 0)$,

then X is called a BCK-algebra. We can define a partial order \leq on X by $x \leq y \iff x * y = 0$. Every BCI-algebra X has the following properties:

- (b1) $(\forall x \in X) (x * 0 = x)$.
- (b2) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * y) * z = (x * z) * y)$.
- (b3) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) (x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x)$.
- (b4) $(\forall x, y \in X) (x * (x * (x * y))) = x * y$.

A Smarandache BCI-algebra [1] is defined to be a BCI-algebra X in which there exists a proper subset Q of X such that

- (s1) $0 \in Q$ and $|Q| \geq 2$,
- (s2) Q is a BCK-algebra under the operation of X .

3. Smarandache Fantastic Ideals

In what follows, let X and Q denote a Smarandache BCI-algebra and a BCK-algebra which is properly contained in X , respectively.

Definition 3.1. [1] A nonempty subset I of X is called a Smarandache ideal of X related to Q (or briefly, Q -Smarandache ideal of X) if it satisfies:

- (c1) $0 \in I$,
- (c2) $(\forall x \in Q) (\forall y \in I) (x * y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I)$.

If I is a ideal of X related to every BCK-algebra contained in X , we simply say that I is a Smarandache ideal of X .

Definition 3.2. [2] A nonempty subset I of X is called a Smarandache fresh ideal of X related to Q (or briefly, Q -Smarandache fresh ideal of X) if it satisfies the condition (c1) and

(c3) $(\forall x, y, z \in Q) ((x * y) * z \in I, y * z \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I)$.

Lemma 3.3. [2] If I is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal of X , then

(i) $(\forall x, y \in Q) ((x * y) * y \in I \Rightarrow x * y \in I)$.

(ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in Q) ((x * y) * z \in I \Rightarrow (x * z) * (y * z) \in I)$.

Definition 3.4. [2] A nonempty subset I of X is called a Smarandache clean ideal of X related to Q (or briefly, Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X) if it satisfies the condition (c1) and

(c4) $(\forall x, y \in Q) (\forall z \in I) ((x * (y * x)) * z \in I \Rightarrow x \in I)$.

Lemma 3.5. [2] Every Q -Smarandache clean ideal is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal.

Lemma 3.6. Let I be a Q -Smarandache ideal of X . Then I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X \iff I satisfies the following condition:

$$(\forall x, y \in Q) (x * (y * x) \in I \Rightarrow x \in I). \quad (1)$$

Proof. Suppose that I satisfies the condition (1) and suppose that $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ for all $x, y \in Q$ and $z \in I$. Then $x * (y * x) \in I$ by (c2), and so $x \in I$ by (1). Conversely assume that I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X and let $x, y \in Q$ be such that $x * (y * x) \in I$. Since $0 \in I$, it follows from (b1) that $(x * (y * x)) * 0 = x * (y * x) \in I$ so from (c4) that $x \in I$. This completes the proof.

Definition 3.7. A nonempty subset I of X is called a Smarandache fantastic ideal of X related to Q (or briefly, Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X) if it satisfies the condition (c1) and

(c5) $(\forall x, y \in Q) (\forall z \in I) ((x * y) * z \in I \Rightarrow x * (y * (y * x)) \in I)$.

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a set with the following Cayley table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
1	1	0	1	0	1	5
2	2	2	0	2	0	5
3	3	1	3	0	3	5
4	4	4	4	4	0	5
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Table 3.1

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a Smarandache BCI-algebra. Note that $Q = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ is a BCK-algebra which is properly contained in X . It is easily checked that subsets $I_1 = \{0, 2\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, 2, 4\}$ are Q -Smarandache fantastic ideals of X , but not Q -Smarandache fresh ideals. A subset $I_3 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal, but not a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal since $(2 * 4) * 3 = 0 \in I_3$ and $2 * (4 * (4 * 2)) = 2 \notin I_3$.

The example above suggests that a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal need not be a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal, and a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal may not be a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal.

Theorem 3.9. Let Q_1 and Q_2 be BCK-algebras which are properly contained in X such that $Q_1 \subset Q_2$. Then every Q_2 -Smarandache fantastic ideal is a Q_1 -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X .

Proof. Straightforward.

The converse of Theorem 3.9 is not true in general as seen in the following example.

Example 3.10. Consider the Smarandache BCI-algebra X described in Example 3.8. Note that $Q_1 := \{0, 2, 4\}$ and $Q_2 := \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ are BCK-algebras which are properly contained in X and $Q_1 \subset Q_2$. Then $I := \{0, 1, 3\}$ is a Q_1 -Smarandache fantastic ideal, but not a Q_2 -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X .

Theorem 3.11. Every Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal is a Q -Smarandache ideal.

Proof. Let I be a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X and assume that $x * z \in I$ for all $x \in Q$ and $z \in I$. Using (b1), we get $(x * 0) * z = x * z \in I$. Since $x \in Q$ and Q is a BCK-algebra, it follows from (a5), (b1) and (c5) that $x = x * (0 * (0 * x)) \in I$ so that I is a Q -Smarandache ideal of X .

As seen in Example 3.8, the converse of Theorem 3.11 is not true in general.

Theorem 3.12. Let I be a Q -Smarandache ideal of X . Then I is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of $X \iff$ it satisfies the following implication:

$$(\forall x, y \in Q) (x * y \in I \Rightarrow x * (y * (y * x)) \in I). \quad (2)$$

Proof. Assume that I is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X and let $x, y \in Q$ be such that $x * y \in I$. Using (b1), we have $(x * y) * 0 = x * y \in I$ and $0 \in I$. It follows from (c5) that $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. Conversely suppose that I satisfies the condition (2). Assume that $(x * y) * z \in I$ for all $x, y \in Q$ and $z \in I$. Then $x * y \in I$ by (c2), and hence $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$ by (2). This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.13. Let I be a nonempty subset of X . Then I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of $X \iff I$ is both a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal and a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X . Then I is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal of X (see Lemma 3.5). Suppose that $x * y \in I$ for all $x, y \in Q$. Since Q is a BCK-algebra, we have

$$(x * (y * (y * x))) * x = (x * x) * (y * (y * x)) = 0 * (y * (y * x)) = 0,$$

and so $(y * x) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) = 0$, that is, $y * x \leq y * (x * (y * (y * x)))$. It follows from (b3), (b2) and (a1) that

$$\begin{aligned} & (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \\ & \leq (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * x) \\ & = (x * (y * x)) * (y * (y * x)) \leq x * y, \end{aligned}$$

that is, $((x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) * (x * y)) = 0 \in I$. Since $x * y \in I$, it follows from (c2) that $(x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \in I$, so from Lemma 3.6 that $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. Using Theorem 3.12, we know that I is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose that I is both a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal and a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X . Let $x, y \in Q$ be such that $x * (y * x) \in I$. Since

$$((y * (y * x)) * (y * x)) * (x * (y * x)) = 0 \in I,$$

we get $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \in I$ by (c2). Since I is a Q -Smarandache fresh ideal, it follows from Lemma 3.3(i) that $y * (y * x) \in I$ so from (c2) that $x * y \in I$ since $(x * y) * (y * (y * x)) = 0 \in I$. Since I is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal, we obtain $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$ by (2), and so $x \in I$ by (c2). Therefore I is a Q -Smarandache clean ideal of X by Lemma 3.6.

Theorem 3.14. (Extension Property) Let I and J be Q -Smarandache ideals of X and $I \subset J \subset Q$. If I is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X , then so is J .

Proof. Assume that $x * y \in J$ for all $x, y \in Q$. Since

$$(x * (x * y)) * y = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0 \in I,$$

it follows from (b2) and (2) that

$$(x * (y * (y * (x * (x * y)))))) * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) \in I \subset J,$$

so from (c2) that $x * (y * (y * (x * (x * y)))) \in J$. Since $x, y \in Q$ and Q is a BCK-algebra, we get $(x * (y * (y * x))) * (x * (y * (y * (x * (x * y)))))) = 0 \in J$, by using (a1) repeatedly. Since J is a Q -Smarandache ideal, we conclude that $x * (y * (y * x)) \in J$. Hence J is a Q -Smarandache fantastic ideal of X by Theorem 3.12.

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